

THE ESSENCE OF SUPPORTIVE RELATIONSHIP FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF NOVICE LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Abstract

Supportive relationship is a crucial need for beginning language teachers whose first years at work after graduating is known to be a pick-and-shovel and challenging stage as they face their adjustment period on developing their career or profession. The purpose of this study was to find the meaning of supportive relationship with superiors and colleagues as a result of the collective experiences of novice language teachers. This research employed phenomenology design through the use of semi-structured interviews. The research participants consisted of novice language teachers with zero to five years of teaching from the Catholic Schools of Mountain Province. The data analysis involved the processes of coding, categorizing and making themes of the essential meanings of the phenomenon. Findings of the study revealed that the individual and collective articulations of 12 novice language teachers consider supportive relationship as a process acknowledging, scaffolding and empowering the novice language teachers by the administrators and colleagues in the institution. This finding is captured in the illustration labelled as "The Strata of Supportive Relationship for Novice Language Teachers". The study concludes that supportive relationship in the workplace builds the beginning career of novice language teachers as they engage themselves to a more efficient work role and professional identity. It is hoped that this study helps in designing supportive practices and measures of transition a neophyte to a competent and effective language teachers. It is recommended that further studies be conducted on the theories and language of acknowledging, scaffolding and empowering.

Keywords: Supportive Relationship, Acknowledging, Scaffolding, Empowering.

INTRODUCTION

In teaching, challenges are brought about by emerging educational programs like the pressures for standards-based teaching, increased multicultural composition of the student population, and parental attitudes such as non-conformity to school policies. In addition to these, teachers experience lower rates of job satisfaction caused by many factors, including a general lack of public support for teaching as a profession (Zeichner, 2003). Based on studies, supportive relationships in the workplace have always been a significant concern for workers (Bainer & Didham, 1994).

Support or Supportive relationship as described by Drury (2008) is a line that exists between a supervisor and an employee, a teacher and the students or an employee and his co-employees that is connected by a kind of psychological channel through which all communications, reactions, and feelings must flow back and forth. Through this relationship channel, each party views, interprets, and reacts to the other. The openness - the amount of freedom or naturalness - of this line contributes to the quality or tone of the relationship, which, in turn, is the essence of the working arrangement.

Researches presented several forms of support experiences of teachers. The study of Viernes and de Guzman (2005) presents descriptions of supportive relationship as it explored on experiences of private elementary and secondary school teachers on supportive relationships with colleagues. Results showed four important descriptions of supportive relationships as (1) a life-giving force; (2) an extension of one's family; (3) a reciprocal process; and (4) a work still in progress. The need for supportive relationship is evident as it adds to efficiency in the work. Teachers with strong affiliation are more effective (Chubb, 1988; Little, 1982; & Rosenholtz, 1985); hence, supportive relationships among teachers have also been linked to higher student achievement and improved classroom discipline (Cohen, & Osterweil, 1986; Little, 1982). Relationships with colleagues were also highlighted by Kelchtermans (1996) and linked it to the concept of good working conditions and as one of the categories of interests necessary to achieve maximum performance of professional tasks. Studies also prove that supportive relationships boost psychologically the novice teacher. In the analyses of Chester and Beaudin (1996), the self-efficacy beliefs of teachers who had received support from experienced teachers in their school were enhanced. In contrast, if little attention was given to novice teachers, self-efficacy beliefs declined.

The findings of Chester and Beaudin (1996) also suggested that putting off the observations until late in the year could lead to negative self-efficacy beliefs for that teacher, because the teacher might feel that the administrator did not value his or her competence.

In addition, the study of Punch and Tuetteman (1996) on psychological distress that was associated with misbehavior of students and excessive societal expectations revealed that teachers' stress could be alleviated by praise and recognition from fellow colleagues. In a qualitative study of student teacher and novice teachers in agricultural education, Knobloch and Whittington (2002) claim that novice teachers felt more efficacious and confident if they received positive feedback, support, guidance, and encouragement from students, teachers, administrators, parents, and community members. Although there can be various means of support and feedback, selected variables of having a mentor, collective efficacy, and principal support appear to be related to teacher efficacy.

Supportive relationship has an impact on teachers' attrition. Teachers, quite often, feel discouraged early in their careers because they feel unsupported by colleagues and administrators (National Commission on Teaching and America's Future, 2003), and studies have also indicated that teachers who leave the organization express dissatisfaction with the level of support and the effectiveness of the leadership of the institutions. As David (2008) posed that organizations with higher levels of administrative support were found to have lower attrition.

Kraft & Papay (2021) in their study highlights the significance of mentoring on novice teachers' performance and retention. It manifests that effective mentoring strategies contribute to the development of supportive relationships which lead to improved teaching quality and teacher retention.

Iacuone (2015) also investigated the type of administrative support that novice science teachers received. After administrative observations, the teachers were engaged in dialogue and were provided the opportunity to attend professional development outside the district.

Support is indispensable for novice teachers to help them face and overcome the challenges and survive in the teaching profession (Karatas & Karaman, 2013). Researches highlight the role of the first years of teaching in a teacher's career and how the experiences of teachers mold their identity and future practices. As argued by Pitton (2006), the success of new teachers is critically linked to their first teaching experiences and the opportunities they are given to talk through issues they face in the classroom. If they are left alone with their challenges and start to feel ineffective, they believe that they are not suitable for the profession and quit their jobs. The increase in the teachers' leaving the profession is attributed to the gap between pre-service education and in-service development. After receiving university education and starting their jobs, novice teachers suddenly have no further contact with their teacher educators, and they experience the same challenges as their more experienced colleagues on the very first day of school without much guidance from their new school (Farrell, 2012). Thus, district leaders and principals concerned with retention of new teachers must work with beginning teachers to ensure that first-year teachers remain optimistic (Chapman, 1984).

With the reviewed studies on the description of supportive relationship (Viernes & de Guzman, 2005), type of administrative support given to novice science teachers (Iacuone, 2015), and impact on teachers' attrition (National Commission on Teaching and America's Future, 2003), as a booster to efficiency of work (Chubb, 1988; Little, 1982; & Rosenholtz, 1985), higher student achievement and improved classroom discipline (Cohen & Osterweil, 1986; Little, 1982), self-efficacy beliefs (Chester & Beaudin, 1996) and efficiency and confidence (Punch & Tuetteman, 1996) of the novice teacher, a dearth of discussion on meaning or essence of supportive relationship as experienced by novice English teachers exist; hence, this study aims to look into the meaning of supportive relationships from the significant experiences of novice teachers. As new teachers strive to develop their teaching in new environments, they encounter various experiences and challenges. Inman, Marlow, and Betancout-Smith (1997) found in their study of over 600 teachers that support from colleagues, particularly people who fill a mentor role, was important for beginning teachers.

Also, in the study of Diab & Green (2024), they emphasized that novice teachers in different socio-cultural arenas need the necessary support systems in order to boost their professional, psychological and emotional needs.

METHODOLOGY

This study made use of the phenomenology design, which defines the concept of intentionality and the meaning of lived experience from the first person point of view (De Guzman, 2013). It employed qualitative interview with novice teachers through semi-structured interviews. Novice teachers in this study had zero to five years of teaching. An

Aide Memoir, which consisted of the participants' robotfoto and the interview question guide facilitated the interview. Validation of interview results were also conducted through triangulation; hence, the participants' administrators and colleagues were also interviewed. The processes of coding, categorizing and making sense of the essential meanings of the phenomenon were employed to analyze the gathered data.

Findings

The collective experiences of the language novice teachers as to the meaning of supportive relationship are embodied in Figure 1. From the perspective of the novice teachers, supportive relationship is the process of acknowledging, scaffolding, and empowering the novice teachers by their colleagues and superiors in the institution.

The figure shows that there is a process that novice teachers experience in supportive relationship. This is shown by the layers/strata in the figure. It starts with acknowledging as the first step, building up to scaffolding, and finally empowering.

Figure 1: The strata of supportive relationship for novice language teachers

Acknowledging

From the experiences of the participants, acknowledging includes the elements of the warm acceptance of colleagues and superiors to the novice teachers, and the establishment of an environment for new teachers to feel a sense of belongingness to the family as verbalized by the participants:

Teacher 12: As a first timer in the teaching profession, I had experienced an adjustment period, but because I found out that my boss as well as my colleagues are approachable and friendly, my adjustment period lasted for a short while. In general, I became

comfortable with them that I didn't find difficulty in approaching them for help or assistance that I needed regarding my works. I can say that I am blessed that they are my companions and head.

Teacher 1: *"Tinatanong nila ako kung ano ang mga kailangan at nararamdaman ko at bawat pagkikita at pagsasalubong ay ngumingiti at nagbabatian kaming lahat. Magaan ang loob namin sa isa't isa kaya di ako nag-aatubiling magtanong o magsabi ng saloobin ko sa kanila."*(They ask me what I need and how I feel. Every time we meet and see each other, we smile and greet one another. We feel at ease with one another so I can readily ask or tell my concerns to them.)

Teacher 4: *ahh...(thinking) para sa 'kin, sa una, tahimik ako dahil baguhan ako at nangangamba akong magkamali. Pero ipinaramdam sa akin nina madam principal at ng aking mga kasamahan na kabilang ako sa pamilya kaya unti-unti akong naging komportable at nasasabi ko ang mga hinaing ko sa kanila tulad ng mga katanungang, ano ang dapat kong gawin dito, kasi nga bago pa ako, dahil din sa madali ko silang nakapanatagang-loob at nakakausap. "For me, at first, I was just quiet since I am new and I am afraid of committing any mistake, but ma'am principal and my co-teachers let me feel that I am a member of the family so, little by little, I felt comfortable and eventually, I was able to air my concerns to them like asking them how to do things since I am a neophyte, because I got acquainted and got close to them."*

Teacher 3: *"Since I am new in the field, I felt a bit of uneasiness and inhibition in dealing with my colleagues since two of them are my mentors in this same school before. The others are new like me; however, as months passed by, we became comfortable with each other since they are very approachable and supportive that I consider them as my second family whom I can undoubtedly share my thoughts and feelings. We often communicate with each other casually. We openly share our joys and problems especially those concerning the school."*

Teacher 10: *"I can say that we have a good relationship with each other as brothers and sisters. Our principal is also like a big sister for me for she is ever approachable when I ask concerns from her."*

Teacher 5: *Ah.. I mean, our principal speaks or tells any concerns in a fatherly and kind manner. He also deals with us as colleagues and not as a head so that I feel at ease and comfortable in telling my problems with regards to school matters and in return, he also addresses these immediately.*

Teacher 6: *"Our school has a healthy working environment so I deal with my colleagues and my superior with respect and humility. As a result of the harmonious relationship between and among us teachers and our administrators, I can say that everybody is approachable."*

The participants recognized that to be a new member in a group or an institution, they have their own fears and expectations. But these feelings of uneasiness and difficulties eventually faded because they felt accepted as members or parts of the school family.

The acceptance they felt from their colleagues and superiors made them reciprocate and nurture the good relationship they developed; thus, they can freely express themselves without reservations. In addition, feeling free and welcomed, the participants felt light in their work despite the pressure. This is evident in the following sharing of the participants:

Teacher 11: *“Aha... for me, probably, I may say that at first it was difficult... but time passed by and I came to know them and then I feel comfortable with them and then you know...I just feel that there is that mutual friendship among us in the work place...and that is what keeps me going!”*

Teacher 7: *I would say that we have a happy relationship for I observed that everyone seems to know how to go with the others. No one acts as more superior than the others. I learned that for as long as we know how to deal with others fairly and nicely, there'll be no problem when it comes to working relationship.*

Teacher 3: *“Being new in the field, it had been always heart-warming when they help me and I really feel the sense of belongingness, thus; the pressure of everyday work becomes lighter.”*

Teacher 1: *“Nakukuha nga po naming magbiruan sa isa't isa kaya parang naiibsan ang pagod at kirot dulot ng kakulitan ng mga estudyante. (We even crack jokes with one another so the pressures from students are somewhat lightened.*

Teacher 9: *Another is when we are given equal opportunity to share our ideas and suggestions that could be of help in terms of planning. I feel inspired and encouraged because of this./ Hmmm, one of my inspiring experiences is when my suggestions were carried during planning of school activities./When we talk with each other we try to use kind and uplifting words. In terms of building good relationships, the use of polite words and encouraging gestures were of help.*

Scaffolding

Scaffolding refers to the support and assistance the novice teacher participants experienced with their administrators and colleagues in the form of mentoring. Forms of support were evident in the areas of instruction, classroom management, students' discipline, and paper works. Surprisingly many of the participants were supported by colleagues and administrators from complaints of parents regarding their children's grade or discipline as shown in the following statements of the participants:

Parents' behavior toward the low or failing grades of their children is a common struggle here in our school. For this, our older colleagues and our administrator whom we consider as our second mothers and elder brother gave us new teachers pieces of advice on how to deal with the parents.

They also support us by helping us explain the grading system as well as the attitudes of their children in school to the parents. By their support, my stressful feelings are comforted. (Teacher 4)

Other participants added their unpleasant encounters with the students' parents:

Some parents blame me for the failing grades of their children. My colleagues, with the help of our principal, supported me in explaining to the parents the why and how of such matter since some parents don't yet know or understand the K-12 grading system. Some parents even hit me below the belt, but in spite of such, I am comforted due to the all-out support from my colleagues and administrator. (Teacher 3)

An unforgettable experience was when a parent, a professional, but did not act as a professional suddenly came to my classroom and without etiquette, confronted me regarding his child's grade. My colleagues and our principal heard the commotion and they came to my aid by calming down the parent 'til we settled in the principal's office for a better atmosphere to talk about his concern. My colleagues and our principal helped me explain how the grade was computed and everyone aired their observations on the actuations and attitude of his child in school. (Teacher 12)

Students' behavior was also easily addressed because of the collaborative efforts and support of colleagues and administrators. In the following, it describes the participants' experience regarding students' discipline:

Behavioral problems of students inside and outside the school campus are problems I am faced with. In times when I cannot discipline/deal with these students, in spite of all the possible interventions that I do, I always refer them to our principal and to the POD (Perfect of Discipline) and they always support me by helping me deal with the misbehaving students. (Teacher 4)

Our principal and my co-teachers supported me when one parent confronted me because I slapped her son due to his misbehavior. They helped me explain the situation to the parent. (Teacher 5)

The following experiences show the support of colleagues and administrators to the novice teachers in the areas of classroom instruction and requirements and extra-curricular activities:

I got support anyway from the younger colleagues, hehe. Olds are for the olds, ika nga. (as they say) When I first began teaching, I was able to go to the younger colleagues for support in everything from classroom management to teaching methods. One colleague helped me with the instruction in the classroom. I remember when he allowed me to observe in his Filipino classes and everyone was so engaged that I wanted my classes to look just like that. (Teacher 5)

Another is regarding the approaches and contents of this K-12 curriculum. It's good that my colleagues share their knowledge and suggestions about it. Our principal also supports us by procuring and securing K-12 references. Ah yes, one good thing from my co-teachers is when they orient and teach me on how to make instructional materials. This is very helpful especially now that we are still groping for some references and instructional materials for the K-12 curriculum. I am inspired because I experience the beauty of helping one another be it in our personal tasks like the computation of grades

and filling up of forms like the cards, the school register, etc. or in group tasks. Everybody is willing to lend a helping hand and as we do so, our principal also is always behind us. (Teacher 7)

Meanwhile, my colleagues who finished their grades ahead since they have fewer number of advisory class helped me in my grades. (Teacher 5)

Well, sa mga activities ng paaralan halimbawa ang SLT (Schools of Living Traditions), ay may mga gawain kaming mga guro, at hindi ko alam ito dahil nag-aral ako sa pampublikong paaralan. Ipinapaliwanag at inaaalalayan ako ni Ma'am principal at mga kasamahan kong mga guro kaya kahit papaano, nakakasabay ako habang natututo ako. Kahit sa ibang mga gawain, damang-dama ko ang suporta ng aking mga kasamahan at punong-guro. (Well, for school activities like for example, the SLT, we were given tasks to do; I am not familiar with such since I had my secondary schooling in a public school. Our principal and my colleagues guided and assisted me with my task so I was able to cope as I learned from the experience. Even in other school tasks, I feel the support of my colleagues and principal.) (Teacher 1)

Ah, okey po...During intramurals for example, I am recommended to be the trainer or coach of the literary contestants for English category; however, the unit advisers help and assist me during the practices. They don't put all the burdens on me. Our principal also comes and gives inputs and suggestions for improvement. This is true in other school tasks that we do. We have the cooperation and team work method. (Teacher 12)

The above statements could be summarized in the sharing made by one participant who said:

"For my colleagues, their concern on coaching, orienting, and assisting me on the tasks and details of our school works and programs since I am new made me feel good." (Teacher 12)

Empowering

Words such as inspiring, authorizing, energizing, and encouraging are terms that describe the experiences of the participants as they were motivated and enabled to grow in their profession. In this study, the experience is described as empowering. Empowering is allowing the participants to innovate and develop themselves after being acknowledged and scaffolded. It is also appreciating the simple details of goodness and good points of the novice teachers.

In my first year of teaching, my experiences are kept in the heart, hehe. I was inspired by the words of praise and appreciation from our principal like when we arrive in school early, when we wear our complete uniforms, and the like; much more when the student I coached won in an essay contest. This served as motivating factor for me. (Teacher 12)

When our principal observed me during observation times, she gave her appreciation on the way I handle my students and the way I teach and I feel good about this. (Teacher 2)

Well, I am inspired when at least, I hear a bit of appreciation or praise from them, hehehe, pampalubag – loob kung baga. (Moral boosting, as they say). An example was when they appreciated me when I translated a declamation piece in English to Filipino, which was delivered by one of our students in a contest. (Teacher 5)

Hmmm..(nodding) sa obserbasyon namin, I mean noong inobserbahan kami sa aming pagtuturo sa classroom ni ma'am principal, binigyang-diin niya ang mga magagandang ginamit at ginawa ko sa aking klase at sa aming mga pagpupulong, sinabi din niya ang mga kapuri-puring ginagawa namin. Dahil dito, parang napapataas ang aking moral at nagaganyak akong ipagpatuloy ang aking mga nasimulan. (Hmmm..[nodding] When we were observed by the principal, she emphasized my good points and during our faculty meetings, she praised our good points. Because of this appreciative gestures from our administrator, my moral is boosted and I am motivated to continue what I've started.) (Teacher 1)

The participants also felt empowered when they felt that their colleagues and superiors believed in their capability and competence to do the works assigned to them as exemplified in the following:

I can say I'm still a novice as compared to my colleagues who've stayed for almost and even more than 10 years in the public service. But I'm glad that these people believed in my capacity and recommended me thus, I was appointed as the School Filipino Key Teacher and School Paper Co-Adviser which is a difficult responsibility though on my part. However, in return I also keep on pushing myself to do my best to serve the school like supporting the school's programs most especially on Filipino concerns. I also lend my expertise in computer literacy and a little knowledge in formal writing. (Teacher 8)

I could not forget when he also recommended me to be the trainer/coach of our participants to an English quiz bee. As a neophyte, I was hesitant but then he encouraged and motivated me to do so. (Teacher 7)

I also receive forms of encouragement from my colleagues. For example, when we had to finish many paper works before the deadline set by the administrators, we boost each other's moral as we help one another to the point of spending time beyond the school hours. (Teacher 11)

Finally, novice teachers are empowered when opportunities for them to grow are encouraged and provided and when they are sent to seminars and got updated on their fields of specialization as indicated in the following verbalizations:

My head also kept on sending me to seminars and workshops which gave means to me to enhance further what I know. (Teacher 8). We are also sent to seminars related to our field of specialization for updating. In addition, teachers' recollection is given at the beginning of the school year for our spiritual, social and moral development for us to be more focused and energized as we go on with our daily teaching career. (Teacher 3). Our head also encourages and allows us to attend seminars for us to be updated and be abreast with the current trends. She also sets schedules for the sharing of highlights and

insights of seminars attended so that our colleagues who did not attend will also be updated. (Teacher 2).

The struggle I encountered during my first teaching is that even if it is not my major, the principal gave that as my teaching load. My principal encouraged me though that it would be a learning and growing avenue for me. I considered it as difficulty because I don't know some of the subject matters but the librarian provided some references for me. My colleagues also gave some words of encouragement. (Teacher 10)

Well, the admin and my closed colleagues, through thick and thin, they are always there for me. They keep on encouraging and pushing me hard to finish my master's degree. (Teacher 8)

As there are many complexities in grammar and since I am new in the field, I encounter problems in my actual teaching, however; our principal did not leave me alone. She made me see and analyze the complexities of my lessons and helped me unravel things. This let me feel that though I am new, I can grow fast through the supportive gestures of my head for she considers us neophytes as her younger children and she rears us to grow robustly. (Teacher 3)

He he he, eto na..(Hehehe, this is it...) One of which is my regional defect in which I'm hard up to pronounce words especially terms with "i" and "e". Another one is when I'm caught in a situations when I can't think of the most appropriate terms to use in a certain statements. Worst thing is when students are not able to understand the important points I'm trying to explain to them. With these weaknesses, my colleagues and administrator helped by giving me encouragements that I can still improve as they gave me advice and points for improvement. (Teacher 9)

DISCUSSION

Though the participants feel the burdens and problems of adjustment being new in the real world of teaching, they acknowledge that the fulfillment and satisfaction they derived from supportive relationships with superiors and colleagues far outweighed the difficulties, frustrations, and struggles resulting from their adjustment, from the pressures of work, from students, and from some conflicts with other stakeholders such as the parents.

The essence of supportive relationship among novice language teachers based on their own experiences during their initial years in the teaching field is reflected in the 'The Strata of Supportive Relationship for Novice Language Teachers.' The figure shows the three stages or the layers of support that the novice teachers have received from their colleagues and administrators. Just like the healthy soil, supportive relationship with administrators and colleagues is the source of nourishment to novice teachers.

This sustenance makes them grow in a holistic manner as they discharge the responsibilities attached to their teaching career. From their entry to the actual field, the acknowledging stratum makes the beginning teachers feel at home in their new environment. As they discharge their daily endeavors, the second stratum, scaffolding

gives them the feeling of sturdy support and security. In facing the multiple tasks in school, the empowering stratum leads them to explore their potentials and capabilities to grow personally and professionally.

Specifically, the acknowledging stratum centers on the experiences of beginning teachers as they are welcomed wholeheartedly as members of the workplace. The simple forms like smiling and nodding, asking the novice teachers their need, using gentle and polite words, being approachable, acting as big brothers and sisters, and listening to the novice teachers' opinion were ways that novice teachers felt comfortable and accepted in the workplace. During the interviews with the administrators and elder colleagues, they truly affirmed that they treat the novice teachers as their youngest children or their younger brothers and sisters or friends who should feel their tender love and care. In this way, it encouraged open communication and the novice teachers were very free to express themselves with their peers as they felt a sense of belongingness. Collegial relationships with peers make it possible to share here-and-now experiences. Moreover, relationships with peers make them feel members of a 'community of practice'. The first year is also a difficult year to adjust and overcome problems for novice teachers. The novice teacher seeks for closeness and belongingness in order for him to be able to voice out his needs, problems as well as his joys and for him to feel at ease for a smooth sailing work condition. Novices freely share their experiences and difficulties experienced with other novices which makes them realize that they are not facing the problems alone, by developing the "I am not alone" feeling. This is also made possible because of the healthy and nurturing work environment they have with administrators and colleagues.

The second stratum of supportive relationship – scaffolding emphasizes on mentoring. The novice teachers have the utmost desire to be surrounded by supportive and concerned heads and co-teachers especially in situations which are not so favorable. Most teachers experienced being confronted by parents regarding their children's grades. In these cases, their superiors and colleagues were always available to support them explain the cases. The concern and support was validated by their colleagues and superiors who claimed that it is a part of their responsibility to stand by them as their older siblings. In this manner, it somehow eases the fear of the novice teachers in entertaining the confronting parents.

The school heads also acknowledged that the new teachers need strong and continuous guidance and support. One of them said, "I have to prioritize providing reference books for them." Naturally, the teachers should have the copies of all materials that will be used in their classes. New teachers might also be loaned such supplementary materials as packets/modules that can be used in their courses, reference dictionaries, grammar books, and professional articles.

Another school head added that beginning teachers need supervision in terms of classroom management and strategies in teaching. To help the teachers, he conducts post conferences where he gives suggestions, and follows them up during faculty meetings and informal conversations. For language teachers, useful information of the language programs and their place in the curriculum need to be discussed. The

development of the curriculum process should draw on the combined energies of the entire staff, teachers, and administrators alike; in this manner, the more effective, and indeed supportive, the processes will be.

It was also clearly verbalized by the new teachers that their older colleagues are willing to help them do their paper works such as entering the grades in the cards or fill out some students' form if they see the new teachers struggling to finish the work in order to beat the deadline. Such acts made the neophytes inspired and supported as they can see from their superiors and colleagues the value of team work. Neophyte teachers may also view administrative and collegial support as helping with student discipline problems, paper work, time management in the classroom, and other tasks in the school.

In the third stratum, empowering - professional growth and development as a significant aspect in the career of novice teachers is encouraged. This was experienced by the teachers as they were provided by the administration the opportunities to explore, discover and enhance their capabilities. Participants claimed that they were always sent to seminars and were encouraged to pursue graduate studies. A program can send its teachers to a national or regional language teaching conference, workshops that are sponsored by the language program itself.

Added to this, teachers can also be encouraged through promotion and salary incentives to further their education. Another form of empowering the new teachers was in the form of giving them the trust to assume responsibilities such as advising in organizations, and coaching students. This opportunity makes the beginning teachers feel the trust of their administrators and colleagues and it pushes them to perform better. Mentoring is usually regarded as something that teachers do in order to bring about changes in learners.

Most importantly, the teacher participants value the effort of the administration and colleagues of motivating them to equip and excel themselves in whatever endeavors they are assigned to or provided with. The participants' orientation and preparation not only professionally but also spiritually at the beginning of the school year is confirmed by one of the principals. He said that together with the novice teachers, they are given a recollection before the start of classes where they could reflect and be energized by the Holy Spirit for them to be able to always take Jesus, the model teacher, as a guide in the discharge of their duties and responsibilities. This yearly activity sets the direction for novice teachers. Based on the discussion, three major themes were identified: 1) acknowledging which shows that the beginning teachers are welcomed wholeheartedly as members of the workplace; 2) scaffolding that emphasizes mentoring from superiors and colleagues alike; and 3) empowering where professional growth and development of the novice teachers is evident and encouraged in the workplace.

These characterize the process of supportive relationship experienced by the novice teachers. To the participants, the positive atmosphere between them and their administrators and colleagues far outnumbered and outweighed some minimal feelings of no support especially during their very first days in the work place which some of the participants shared.

CONCLUSIONS

Supportive relationship is the process of acknowledging, scaffolding, and empowering the novice teachers by their colleagues and superiors in the institution. It further shows the crucial roles of administrators and colleagues in building the teaching career of beginning teachers. Administrators and colleagues serve as older siblings who are ready to receive beginning teachers and help create a conducive work environment and further serve as buffers and shield to the neophyte teachers from anything and anyone that destructs them to discharge their responsibilities. Colleagues and administrators are motivators who empower new teachers to discover and expand their potentials. With this study, it is hoped to help in designing supportive practices and ways of enhancing teachers' transition from a neophyte to a competent and effective teachers.

Acknowledgement

Accomplishing all the tasks associated with research requires much reading, thinking, and analysis, as it also demands time and effort. Not all of the ideas, time and effort expended to complete this project was by the author. The researcher expresses her profound gratitude to the following for without their efforts and contributions, this research could not have been completed.

She would like above all, to thank heavenly Father, for giving her His graces, guidance, and strength which propelled her to complete this study; Mountain Province State Polytechnic College (MPSPC), now Mountain Province State University (MPSU) for allowing her to conduct this study for professional growth; The Catholic Schools of Mountain Province (CSMP) Family - the administrators and teachers, for accommodating her request as participants of this study and for sharing their precious time for the interviews in spite of their hectic schedules and school works; Her family: mama Bernardita, husband Noel and five children namely Celestie, Phelcarl Leyzen, Xandrelle Leiz and Xandrech Leih (twin), and Janoelle Lexiane for their understanding when her studies prevented her from giving the attention they deserve and for inspiring her and accepting the role of supporting cast throughout the entire process; and to friends, relatives and colleagues and to all who in one way or another had contributed for the success of this research endeavor. To all of you, she extends her deepest gratitude as she humbly dedicates to you this piece of work!

References

- 1) ANGELL, C. and B. GARFINKEL, 2002. The Power of Mentoring Beginning Teachers Glen Forest Elementary School Journal. June 2002. Vol.1.
- 2) ALTMAN, I. and D. TAYLOR, 1987. The development of interpersonal relationships. Communication in interpersonal relationships: Social penetration theory. New York: Holt, Rinehart, and Winston.
- 3) BAINER, D. and C. DIDHAM, 1994. Mentoring and other support behaviors in elementary schools. Journal of Educational, in de Guzman, A.B. and Viernes, R.M. (2005). Filipino teachers' experiences of supportive relationships with colleagues: A Narrative-biographical inquiry. Education Research Institute 2005, Vol. 6 (2): 137-142. Asia Pacific Education Review.
- 4) BAKER, V. D. 2007. Relationship between job satisfaction and the perception of administrative support among early career secondary choral music educators. Journal of Music Teacher Education, Vol.17 (1): 77-90.
- 5) BERMAN, E.M. RICHTER Jr. and R. J. WEST, 2002. Workplace relations: Friendship patterns and consequences (According to managers). Public Administration Review.

- 6) BRANNAN, D. and T. BLEISTEIN, 2012. Novice ESOL teachers' perceptions of social support networks. *TESOL Quarterly*, Vol. 46 (3): 539-541.
- 7) BROWN, J. D. 2009. *The elements of language curriculum*. Heinle and Heinle Publishers. Boston, Massachusetts USA.
- 8) CLANDININ, D.J. and F. M. CONNELLY, 2000. *Narrative inquiry experience and story in qualitative research*. San Francisco: Jossey - Bass Publishers.
- 9) CLARK, S. K. and BYRNES 2012. *The plight of the novice teacher*. Clearing House. Vol. 7
- 10) COATES and THORESEN, 1976 in Terry, P., 1997. *Teacher burnout: Is it real? Can we prevent it?* Texas .ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. 408 258.
- 11) COHEN, E. and Z. OSTERWEIL, 1986. An "issue-focused" model for mental health consultation with groups of teachers. *Journal of School Psychology in de Guzman, A.B. and Viernes, Ramona M. 2005. Filipino teachers' experiences of supportive relationships with colleagues: A narrative-biographical inquiry*. Education Research Institute 2005, Vol. 6, No. 2: 137-142. *Asia Pacific Education Review*.
- 12) CRESWELL, J. 2008. *Educational research: planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. 3rd ed. New Jersey: Pearson Education.
- 13) CURTIS, C. and D. WISE, 2012. *Mathematics teachers speak out - Why are we losing our new teachers?* *National Teacher Education Journal*, 5(2): 75-81.
- 14) DANIELSON, L. 2004. *Developing and retaining quality classroom teachers through mentoring*. The Clearing House.
- 15) DAVID, J. L. 2008. *What research says about.../ Teacher recruitment incentives*. *Educational Leadership Journal*, Vol. 65, No. 7. *Poverty and Learning*: 84-86.
- 16) DENZIN, N. K. and Y. S. LINCOLN, Eds. 1998. *The landscape of qualitative research: Theories and issues*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- 17) DECI, E. L. and RYAN, R.M. 1985. *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. New York: Plenum Press.
- 18) DECI, E. L. et al.1994. *Facilitating internalization: the self-determination theory perspective*. *Journal of Personality*. Vol. 12.
- 19) DE GUZMAN, A. B. & R. M. VIERNES, 2005. *Filipino teachers' experiences of supportive relationships with colleagues: A narrative-biographical inquiry*. Education Research Institute 2005, Vol. 6, No. 2, 137-142. *Asia Pacific Education Review*.
- 20) DE GUZMAN, A. B. 2013. *Qualitative research: Designs and processes (Seminar information map)*. abdeguzman@mnl.ust.edu.ph.
- 21) DIAB, A., & GREEN, E. 2024. *Cultivating Resilience and Success: Support Systems for Novice Teachers in Diverse Contexts*.
- 22) DORNYEI, Z. & T. MURPHY. 2003. *Group dynamics in the language classroom*. Cambridge University Press.
- 23) DRURY, D. 2008. *Improving productivity*. *Human Resource Development Review*, Vol.1: 66-90.
- 24) EUROPEAN COMMISSION. Directorate-General for Education and Culture. 2010. *Developing coherent and system-wide induction programs for novices: a handbook for policymakers*. Brussels.
- 25) FARRELL, T. S. C. 2012. *Novice-Service language teacher development: Bridging the gap between pre-service and in-service education and development*. *TESOL Quarterly*, 46(3): 435-449.

- 26) FEIMAN-NEMSER, S. 1996. Teacher mentoring: A critical review. ERIC Digest. Washington, DC: ERIC Clearinghouse on Teaching and Teacher Education.
- 27) FÖRBOM, M. 2003. Mentori: Aloittelevan opettajan käsikirja [The mentor: Manual for a beginning teacher].
- 28) GAGNE, M. and DECI, E. L. 2005. Self-determination theory and work motivation. John Wiley and Sons, Ltd.
- 29) GOODWIN, M.A. 2008. The micro-political boundary: Navigating political cultures during the first three years of teaching. Available from ProQuest Dissertation and Theses database. (UMI No. 3319529).
- 30) GRAEN, B. and M. UHL-BIEN 1995. Relation-based approach to leadership: Development of leader-member exchange (lmx) theory of leadership over 25 years applying a multi-level multi-domain perspective. Leadership Quarterly 6:2. JAI Press, Inc.
- 31) HAYNES, L. 2011. Novice teachers' perceptions of their mentoring experiences. Pro Quest Dissertations and Theses (PQDT). Retrieved from: <http://search.proquest.com/docview/922678446?accountid=13014>, Accessed on August 2014.
- 32) HOLLOWAY, and H. JOHN, 2001. Research link/ the benefits of mentoring. Leadership Journal May 2001, Vol. 58 No. 8. Who is teaching our children?: 85-86.
- 33) HUSSERL. 1970. in de Guzman, A. B. 2013. Qualitative research: Designs and Processes (Seminar information map). abdeguzman@mnl.ust.edu.ph.
- 34) IACUONE, L. 2015. Administrative support of novice science teachers: a multiple case study. Clemson University.
- 35) INGERSOL. 2011. The challenges facing beginning teachers. Bartell 01.qxd, July 21, 2004.
- 36) INGERSOLL, R. M. 2001. Teacher turnover and teacher shortages: An organizational analysis. American Educational Research Journal. Vol.15.
- 37) INMAN, D., MARLOW, L. and BETANCOURT-SMITH M. 1997. Beginning teachers: are they still leaving the profession? The Clearing House.
- 38) KARAMAN, C. A. and P. KARATAS 2013. Challenges faced by novice language teachers: Support, identity, and pedagogy in the initial years of teaching. A Middle East Technical University Northern Cyprus Campus, School of Foreign Languages, Cyprus Middle East Technical University, Faculty of Education, Ankara karatas@metu.edu.tr cendel@metu.edu.tr cation, 14 (1). Retrieved from <http://cie.asu.edu>. Accessed September 2014.
- 39) KIM, K. and G. ROTH, 2011. Novice teachers and their acquisition of work-related information. Current issues in education, Vol. 14(1). Retrieved from <http://cie.asu.edu/>, June 2015.
- 40) KING, L. et al. 1995. Family support inventory for workers: a new measure of perceived social support from family members. Journal of Organizational Behavior, Vol.10. John Wiley and Sons, Ltd.
- 41) KNOBLOCH, N. A. and M. S. WHITTINGTON 2002. Novice teachers' perceptions of support, teacher preparation, quality, and student teaching experience related to teacher efficacy. Journal of Vocational Education Research, 13.
- 42) Kraft, M. A., & Papay, J. P. 2021. Supporting novice teachers: Evidence from a randomized controlled trial of mentoring. Educational evaluation and policy analysis, 43(3), 345-368.
- 43) LAM, B. and H. YAN 2011. Beginning teachers' job satisfaction: the impact of school based factors on teacher development.
- 44) LEPPA, L., REMMIKA, M. and KONIA I. 2001. Novice teachers' work place experiences of collegiate support. University of Tartu, Institute of Educational Sciences 2001.

- 45) LICHTMAN, R.L. 2007. Effects of an organization's climate on performance of supply chain managers in Michigan: a perception study. *International Journal of Quality and Productivity Management*, Vol. 7, No. 1 December 15, 2007.
- 46) LONG, S. 2004. Separating rhetoric from reality. *Journal of Teacher Education*, Vol. 55(2): 141-153.
- 47) LUTON, 2010. in de Guzman, A. B. 2013. Qualitative research: Designs and processes (Seminar information map). abdeguzman@mnl.ust.edu.ph.
- 48) LUTON, L. S.2010. Qualitative research approaches for public administration. New York: M.E. Sharpe.
- 49) MANJULA, C. 2007. A study on personality factors causing stress among school teachers. *language in India: Strength for today and bright hope for tomorrow*, Volume 12: 2 February 2012 ISSN 1930-2940.
- 50) MCEWANA, H. et. al. 2003. Mentoring as a journey. *Teaching and Teacher Education*.
- 51) MCKERROW, K. 1996. Support then solutions: The supervision of teachers. The Clearing House.
- 52) MILLER, J., H.C. BUTTS, and D. Rode 2002 Communication and cooperation. *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*, Vol. 47.
- 53) MULTANEN, L. et al. 2004. Parempi työyhteisö [The better work community]. Helsinki: Finnish Institution for Occupational Health.
- 54) National Commission on Teaching and America's Future. 2003. No dream denied: A pledge to America's children. Washington, D.C.
- 55) ONTARIO COLLEGE OF TEACHERS.121 Bloor Street East Toronto ON M4W 3M5 Telephone: 416-961-8800 Toll-free in Ontario: 1-888-534-2222 E-mail: info@oct.ca www.
- 56) PITTON, D. E. 2006. Mentoring novice teachers: Fostering a dialogue process. 2nd ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- 57) POLKINGHORNE, D. E. 1995. Narrative configuration in qualitative analysis, in Hach, J.A. and Wisniewski, R. (Eds.), *Life history and narrative*. The Falmer Press. London.
- 58) PORTNER, H. 2001. Training mentors is not enough. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- 59) PUNCH, K. F. and E. TUETTEMAN 1996. Reducing teacher stress: The effects of support in the work environment. *Research in Education*, Vol.56.
- 60) ROBBINS, S. F. and JUDGE, T. A. 2007. *Organizational behavior*. 12th Ed. New York: Pearson Education Inc.
- 61) RUHLAND, S.K. and C.D. BREMER, 2002. Professional development needs of novice career and technical education teachers. *Journal of Career and Technical Education* 2002. Vol. 19 No.1.
- 62) TOWERS, J. 2012. Administrative supports and curricular challenges: New teachers enacting and sustaining inquiry in schools. *Canadian Journal of Education*, 35(1): 259-278.
- 63) WEISS, E.M. 1999. Perceived workplace conditions and first-year teacher's morale, career choice commitment, and planned retention: a secondary analysis. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, Vol. 15:861–879.
- 64) ZEICHNER, K. M. 2003. The adequacies and inadequacies of three current strategies to recruit, prepare, and retain the best teachers for all students. *Teachers' College Record*, 105(3): 490–519.